
Role of the Discussion Method in Increasing Student Learning Motivation in Christian Education Subjects

Rico Herbet Sigalingging^{1*}, Senida Harefa², Dorlan Naibaho³

Tarutung State Institute for Christian Studies, Indonesia | rcosigalingging1212@gmail.com¹

Tarutung State Institute for Christian Studies, Indonesia | senidaharefa@gmail.com²

Tarutung State Institute for Christian Studies, Indonesia | dorlan_naibaho@gmail.com³

Correspondence Author*

Abstract

This study discusses the role of the discussion method in increasing student motivation in Christian Religious Education subjects. The purpose of this research is to identify how the discussion method can influence students' learning motivation and why this method is effective in the context of Christian Religious Education subjects. The research was conducted using a qualitative approach by collecting data through classroom observations, interviews with teachers and students, and analysis of documents related to the curriculum. The results of the research show that the discussion method has a significant role in increasing students' learning motivation, by encouraging active participation, exchange of ideas, and a deeper understanding of the material. Factors such as an inclusive classroom environment, teacher facilitation, and student involvement in discussions also play a role in the effectiveness of this method. Therefore, it is recommended that the discussion method be integrated more broadly into Christian Religious Education learning in order to improve the quality of learning and student motivation.

Keywords: Role, discussion method, learning motivation, Christian religious education

Introduction

Education has a very important role in shaping character and preparing the younger generation to face life's challenges. In the context of religious education, learning is not only related to material mastery, but also to the formation of students' moral and spiritual values. Christian Religious Education as part of the curriculum has the goal of developing students' understanding of Christian religious teachings and encouraging spiritual growth.

One important aspect of learning is student motivation. Motivation to learn acts as a driving force for students to be actively involved in the learning process. However, in reality, many students experience problems in maintaining a high level of motivation in certain subjects, including Christian Religious Education. Factors such as boredom, lack of

engagement, and perceived lack of relevance of the material can hinder students' motivation in learning (Ariawan et al., 2023).

In overcoming this challenge, learning methods have a crucial role. One of the learning methods that have been widely applied is the discussion method. The discussion method allows students to actively participate in sharing opinions, exchanging ideas, and deep understanding of the subject matter (Ariawan, 2018). In the context of Christian Religious Education, this method can help students to better understand religious teachings and relate them to everyday life.

This study aims to explore the role of the discussion method in increasing student motivation in the subject of Christian Religious Education. By understanding how the discussion method can influence student learning motivation, it is hoped that solutions can be found to improve the quality of Christian Religious Education learning and overcome the challenges faced by students in maintaining learning motivation. Through a qualitative approach, this study will explore the views of teachers and students and analyze the effects of the application of the discussion method in the Christian Religious Education learning environment.

Research Method

The research was conducted using a qualitative approach by collecting data through classroom observations, interviews with teachers and students, and analysis of documents related to the curriculum. The data obtained from the informants were then reduced. The results of data reduction can be interpreted into useful explanations. Triangulation is used to ensure the validity of the data that has been obtained.

Result/Findings

A. Understanding the Method of Discussion

In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, discussion is an interaction of communication between two or more people. According to Suyanto and Asep Jihad regarding the discussion method, basically it is a process of exchanging information, opinions, and elements of experience on a regular basis with the aim of obtaining a clearer and more thorough understanding of the problem or topic being discussed (Hassama, 2023).

Furthermore, according to Killen the discussion method is a learning method that exposes students to a problem. The discussion method is a method in which the teacher provides opportunities for students (groups) of students to hold scientific discussions in order to gather opinions, make conclusions, or compile various alternative solutions to problems.

From the several opinions above, the authors conclude that the discussion method is a process of communication interaction carried out by two or more people in exchanging information, opinions regarding a topic of problem discussed together in a scientific

conversation aimed at gathering information, making conclusions, compiling various alternative solutions to problems.

1. Purpose of the discussion method

According to Suyanto A. Jihad, the purpose of applying the discussion method to the teaching and learning process is to encourage students to think critically, encourage students to express their opinions freely, motivate students to contribute their thoughts in solving problems together, take one or several alternative answers in solving problems based on careful consideration (Irwan, 2018).

Meanwhile, according to Pupuh Fatuhrrohman "The purpose of using the discussion method is to motivate and stimulate students to think with deep reflection" (Hamenda et al., 2022). According to Muhibbin Syah quoted by Roymond H. Simamora regarding the purpose of the discussion method in the teaching and learning process are: a) encouraging students to think critically, b) encouraging students to express their opinions freely, c) encouraging students to contribute their ideas to solve problems together, d) take one or several alternative answers to solve the problem based on careful consideration (Utari & Mulyanti, 2023).

From the several opinions above, the authors conclude that the purpose of the discussion method is provide stimulation for critical thinking, encourage students to express their opinions freely accompanied by motivating to contribute ideas or thoughts to solve the problem together with a variety of alternative answers to solve problems based on careful consideration.

2. Types of discussion

Budi Santoso put forward two kinds of discussions, namely: a) class discussions, the trainer directs and controls the discussions in a structured manner (so that the objectives are achieved), b) Group discussions, training participants are divided into small groups with predetermined topics (Kristina & Ariawan, 2020). The trainees speak informally and freely in expressing opinions. The division of the trainees into groups (about 5 people) can help keep the trainees involved.

According to Muhammad Anwar, there are five types of discussions, namely:

- a. Formal discussion. This type of discussion is often found in governmental or quasi-governmental institutions, where in this discussion it is necessary to have a chairperson and a writer as well as a formally regulated speaker.
- b. Informal discussion. This type of discussion is often found in study groups where each other is in a face-to-face relationship.
- c. Panel discussion. This type of discussion is often found in various talk shows, especially in electronic media or in scientific seminar forums. The topics discussed are usually discussed by several panelists, with different points of view. Generally, this panel is carried out by only a few people, which can also be attended by several listeners.
- d. Discussion in the form of a symposium. This type is usually found in scientific events that are full of contradictions and dissent.
- e. Lecture discussion. This discussion is carried out by exposing a problem, then discussed. Here usually only one problem, the material being discussed.

From some of the opinions above, the author concludes that the types of discussions are types that take various forms of rules and placement of use according to the type of discussion such as class discussions, group discussions, panel discussions, whole groups, buzz, groups, fish bowls, symposium colloquiums, lecture discussions. and formal discussion, informal discussion.

3. The steps of the discussion method

According to Mulyasa quoted by Warni Tune Sumar & Intan Abdul Razak regarding the steps of the discussion method, as follows: a) formulation of objectives and problems that will be used as topics of discussion, b) prepare the necessary facilities and infrastructure for discussion, c) arrange roles the role of students in the discussion according to the type of discussion being conducted, d) give sufficient direction to students so that they involve themselves actively in discussion activities, e) create a conducive atmosphere so that students can express opinions freely to solve the problems being discussed, f) give opportunities to students in an organized manner so that discussions are not dominated by a few people, g) adjust the holding of discussions to the time available.

According to Abdul Majida, in order for the discussion to be successful, it is necessary to take the following steps:

- a. Prep step. The things that must be considered in preparing for the discussion include:
 - Formulate goals to be achieved, both general and specific goals;
 - Determine the types of discussions that can be carried out in accordance with the objectives to be achieved;
 - Determine the issues to be discussed;
 - Prepare everything related to the technical implementation of the discussion, for example classrooms with all the facilities, discussion officers such as moderators, note takers, and the formulation team, if needed.
- b. Implementation of the discussion. Some things that need to be considered in carrying out the discussion are as follows:
 - Checking all preparations that are considered to affect the smooth running of the discussion.
 - Provide guidance prior to holding the discussion, for example presenting the objectives to be achieved and the discussion rules according to the type of discussion to be held.
 - Carry out discussions in accordance with the rules of the game that have been set. In conducting discussions, you should pay attention to a pleasant learning atmosphere or climate, for example, not calm, not cornering each other and so on.
 - Providing equal opportunity to all discussion participants to share their ideas.
 - Controlling the conversation to the subject matter to the subject being discussed.
 - This is very important because without control the direction of the discussion usually becomes widened and unfocused.
- c. Close the discussion. At the end of the process by using discussion, things should be done as follows:

- Make the main points of discussion as a conclusion in accordance with the results of the discussion.
- Reviewing the course of the discussion by asking for opinions from all participants as feedback for further improvement.

According to M. Yaumi regarding the discussion steps, namely a) giving a brief explanation of the rules of the discussion game including conveying the goals to be achieved, b) carrying out the discussion based on the rules or agreements that have been set, c) giving equal opportunity to each discussion participant to issue ideas and ideas, d) controlling the discussion on the subject matter being discussed so as not to widen and get out of the context of the problem, e) emphasizing the main points of discussion as a way to conclude the results of the discussion, f) reflecting on the various opinions that have been put forward as material for provided feedback and corrections at a later date.

Based on some of the opinions above, the authors conclude that the steps of the discussion method can be started from the preparatory step by being briefed on the rules to be implemented before the discussion, then formulating objectives, defining problems, and emphasizing the main points of discussion as a way to conclude the results of the discussion.

4. Strengths and weaknesses of the discussion method

- a. Advantages of the discussion method. The discussion method has advantages and disadvantages. According to Thomas Edison excess discussion method, namely:
 - This method can encourage, motivate, and stimulate the students to want to think critically, be able to express their opinions, and want and able to contribute his thoughts to solve problems or problems that are faced.
 - If the discussion is carried out properly, a correct answer will be obtained clear and actual.
 - The series of answers taken are based on careful consideration and thorough.

Suyanto and asep stated the advantages of the discussion method, as follows:

- The class atmosphere will be lively because students direct their thoughts to the issues being discussed;
- Make students aware that problems can be solved in various ways;
- Familiarize students to listen to other people's opinions even if they are different from theirs.
- Increasing individual student personality achievements, such as tolerance, democratic, critical, systematic thinking, self-confidence and so on;
- Discussion conclusions are easy for students to understand because they follow and are involved in the thought process before arriving at a conclusion.

Zainal Aqib and Ali Murtadlo argued about the advantages of the discussion method in the learning process, including students learning to consult, respect and respect one another, students got the opportunity to test each other's level of knowledge, the class atmosphere was more lively and dynamic, students can learn to respect the opinions of others, can increase individual personality achievements such as tolerance, democratic attitude, critical attitude,

systematic thinking, and so on, useful for everyday life, especially in a democracy, develop scientific ways of thinking and attitudes, enhance student participation, to express their opinions, both individually and in groups, stimulate students to find ways to solve problems faced together, by deliberating and consulting together, practicing dynamic and creative attitudes in thinking, fostering tolerance in opinions and attitudes, the results of the discussion can be concluded and easy to understand, broaden the horizons and insight into the thinking of the discussion participants.

From the several opinions above, the authors conclude that the advantages of the discussion method are providing encouragement, motivation and learning to think critically in solving problems, respecting the opinions of others, the results of the discussion can be concluded and easy to understand.

b. Weaknesses of the discussion method

Suyanto and Asep Djihad pointed out the weaknesses of the discussion method, namely the possibility that there are students who do not actively participate in the discussion, because for them the discussion is an opportunity to escape from the responsibility and supervision of the teacher, the discussion participants receive limited information, the discussion forum can be controlled by other people. smart people just like to talk.

Thomas Edison stated that there are several weaknesses in using the discussion method:

- This method takes a long time, and the number of students who have to a little.
- This method requires that students have a good background enough about the topic or problem discussed.
- This method is not appropriate to use in the early stages of the learning process if the participants new students are introduced to new learning materials.
- Students who are not used to speaking in forums become apathetic.

According to Zainal Aqib and Ali Murtadlo, there are weaknesses in the discussion method understood, a) namely the opinions and questions of students can deviate from the subject problems, b) difficulty in concluding often causes no resolution, c) requires quite a lot of time, d) the possibility of students who are not actively involved used as an opportunity to play around and disturb other friends, d) when the class atmosphere cannot be mastered, the possibility of using time becomes ineffective and can result in teaching objectives not being achieved, e) it is difficult to predict the direction of completion discussion. This happens if the discussion process is only a place for differences of opinion there is no end to the solution, f) students have difficulty getting out opinion systematically. Especially for students who have shyness and taste afraid of expressing opinions, g) difficulty finding actual discussion themes, which are warm and interesting to discuss.

From the several opinions above, the authors conclude that the weakness of the discussion is that in the learning process takes place by holding discussions, there is a lack of time and will not be resolved at that time, not all students are able to express their opinions, it is difficult to conclude so that it is not resolved.

B. Learning Motivation for Christian Religious Education

1. Definition of learning motivation in Christian religious education

The term motivation can be interpreted as the power contained within the individual, which causes the individual to act or act. Christian Religious Education is a teaching and learning process based on the Bible, Christ-centered and dependent on the Holy Spirit. A Christian education. Teacher must be able to place his presence and function as a reliable facilitator and motivator.

Motivation is the force that drives individual activities to carry out activities to achieve goals. Motivation can also be said as a plan for success to avoid life's failures. In other words, motivation is a process to achieve a goal. Decreased motivation and boredom in class can lead to disciplinary problems.

Dalyono said that "motivation is the mover/motivator to do a job. Which comes from within or also from outside. Motivation that comes from within (intrinsic), namely encouragement that comes from the heart, generally because of awareness of the importance of something. Or it could also be due to encouragement of talent if there is compatibility with the field being studied. Motivation that comes from outside (extrinsic), namely encouragement that comes from outside oneself (environment), for example from parents, teachers, friends and community members. someone who learns with strong motivation, will carry out all his learning activities seriously, passionately or passionately. On the other hand, learning with weak motivation will be lazy and don't even want to do assignments related to learning (Dalyono, 2018).

Apart from the opinion above, Sardiman said that "motivation can be said to be the overall driving force within students that generates learning activities, which guarantees the continuity of learning activities and which gives direction to learning activities so that the goals desired by the learning object can be achieved" (Putra, 2021).

Furthermore, Slameto said that "motivation in the learning process must be considered what can encourage students to study well or have the motivation to think and focus attention, plan and carry out activities related/supporting learning" (Anggraini, 2020).

In this regard, according to Simatupang et al, the definition of Christian Education is divided into two, namely the definition in general and the definition in particular. The definition in general is the process of transmitting the great mandate to implement taxonomic crystallization, while the definition in particular is the process of transmitting Christian knowledge based on the Bible which seeks to implement learning objectives with the support of various sciences. Specific definitions produce attitudes (affective), knowledge (cognitive), and skills (psychomotor) to implement the crystallization of values according to the learning objectives of Christian Education (Simatupang et al., 2020).

The above understanding provides an explanation that the motivation to learn Christian Education is a psychological factor and driving force for students to carry out learning activities. Students who have motivation will be happy and eager to learn. And conversely, if students do not have motivation students will not be serious about learning and good learning

goals will not be achieved. Christian Education is an effort to educate believers including students to have faith in God in Jesus Christ by carrying out a learning process. Because Christian Religious Education is a conscious, systematic and continuous effort whatever its form. Christian Education is an integral part of God's mission that can grow and live and is rooted in God's word. In Proverbs 22:6 it says "Educate a young person according to the way of the Lord that is proper for him, so that even when he is old, he will not deviate from that path". From the text, it can be seen that people who were equipped with God's word in their youth would not deviate from the truth they had obtained.

2. Characteristics of having motivation to learn Christian education

Within each student must have different motivations, so a Christian religious education teacher really needs to know what kind of motivation is in students. According to Mohamad, the characteristics of motivation are:

- a. Diligently facing the task (can work continuously for a long time, not stopping before it's finished).
- b. Tenacious in the face of adversity (not easily discouraged)
- c. Does not require external encouragement to achieve.
- d. Want to explore the material or field of knowledge provided
- e. Always try to achieve as best as possible (not quickly satisfied with his achievements)
- f. Show interest in various adult problems.
- g. Happy and studious, full of enthusiasm, quickly bored with routine tasks can defend his opinions (if you are sure of something, it is not easy to let go of the things you believe in)
- h. Pursue long-term goals (can delay the satisfaction of momentary needs to be achieved later).
- i. Happy to find and solve questions.

Furthermore, according to Sardiman, the motivation that exists in each student has the following characteristics

- a. Persevere in facing the task. Students can work continuously for long periods of time, never stopping before finishing.
- b. Tenacious in the face of adversity (not easily discouraged). There is no need for encouragement from the outside to perform as well as possible (not to quickly break up with the achievements that have been achieved).
- c. Shows interest in a variety of issues. There is an interest or willingness to solve problems that occur in the environment. Students who have high motivation will show an interest in various existing problems by studying these problems.
- d. Prefer to work independently. Willing to work alone without having to be told by anyone and still carry out work happily and seriously.
- e. Get bored quickly in routine tasks. Students will get bored if the tasks are given repeatedly, because then students become creative.
- f. Can defend his opinion. Students will continue to defend their own opinions if they are sure of their opinions without hesitation, even students will be able to state the reasons for each opinion they have.

- g. It's not easy to let go of things you believe in. In this case students have strong self-confidence and are responsible for what is said, and are critical of learning.
- h. Enjoys finding and solving problems. In learning, students who like to find and solve problems are students who think creatively and are active in learning. Through this, students can improve their learning achievement.

Then Junihot stated "High motivation to learn is reflected in persistence that is not easily broken to achieve success even though it is confronted by various difficulties." The characteristics of motivation will be wrong if motivation is considered as an absolute prerequisite for learning activities. It is better to think of it as an ordinary willingness to enter a learning situation. There is no need to delay a learning activity until there is the right motivation to study (Nababan, 2020).

The author can understand that a student who has a high motivation to study Christian Religious Education will study diligently even though there are many difficulties encountered. Apart from having the perseverance to study Christian Religious Education. Sigawa stated "It is the Holy Spirit who is able to give cheerfulness, joy in the heart, so that you are eager to learn the knowledge of faith". The author understands that someone who has the motivation to study Christian Religious Education will be happy and cheerful because of the presence of the Holy Spirit within him who leads him to learn the truth. To enjoy the Spirit's intervention, the teacher needs to invite students to really give up learning activities through prayer and short worship before and after learning (Barton, 2019).

From the opinion above, the writer can conclude that students who have learning motivation will keep working and trying to achieve what is needed. The characteristics of such motivation are very important in teaching and learning activities. In teaching and learning activities will work well if students are diligent in doing assignments, tenacious in solving various problems and obstacles independently. Students who study well will not get stuck.

3. Learning motivation function Christian education

In teaching and learning activities motivation has a very important function. With motivation, students can develop activities and initiatives that are useful for directing and maintaining perseverance and carrying out learning activities. According to Sardiman that there are three functions of motivation, namely:

- a. Encouraging humans to act, namely as a mover or motor that releases energy. Motivation in this case is the driving force in every activity that will be carried out.
- b. Determine the direction of action, namely towards the goal to be achieved. Thus, motivation can provide direction and activities that must be carried out in accordance with the formulation of the objectives.
- c. Selecting actions, namely determining what actions must be carried out in harmony in order to achieve the goal, by setting aside actions that are not beneficial to that goal.

Then Dimyanti & Mudjiono stated that "The function of motivation for students is 1) to make students aware of their position at the beginning of learning, processes and results. 2) provide information about the position of the learning effort, which is compared with peers. 3)

teach learning activities. 4) raising the spirit of learning. 5) awareness of the existence of a learning journey and then continuous learning, individuals are trained to use their strengths in such a way that they succeed (Kim, 2019).

Furthermore, According to Priansa, there are four motivational functions for students, namely:

- a. Encourage action. Motivation is the driving force or motor that releases student energy.
- b. Determine the direction of action. Determinants of direction so that it leads to the goals to be achieved by students.
- c. Selecting actions. Determine various actions that must be done by students to achieve goals, by setting aside various actions that are not useful.
- d. Business booster and achievement. Students do everything because of motivation. Motivation is a trigger for achievement.

In accordance with the opinion above, the authors conclude that motivation can encourage behavior, and motivation can provide direction, as well as activities that must be done and at the same time direct these actions in a more positive direction. So as to produce good learning outcomes. The function of Christian religion education learning motivation is an effort to achieve learning goals in knowing Allah and believing in Him and applying them in their lives. An encounter with God can only occur through the faithfulness of students who proactively read the Bible and pray, so that they truly know and have intimate fellowship with the Lord Jesus. Students' encounters with God, interactions with the Christian community both among fellow students, and with teachers will result in a transformation of faith and ultimately give birth to a transformation of life as a result of getting to know the Lord Jesus and His works.

4. Factors influencing motivation to learn Christian education

Motivation is an active energy that causes a change in a person seen in psychiatric symptoms. According to Iskandar, the factors that influence learning motivation are:

a. Internal motivation (intrinsic motivation)

Internal motivation is the driving force from within a person to do something to achieve the desired goal. In learning activities, internal motivation is the driving force of an individual (student) to continue learning based on a need and encouragement that is absolutely related to learning activities. The point is that internal motivation arises from within an individual student (student) in learning activities that are in accordance with or in line with their needs. For example, if a student is interested in becoming a teacher, then the motivation of the student is that when he graduates from school, he must continue his studies at higher education through the faculty of education.

b. External motivation (extrinsic motivation)

Extrinsic motivation is the driving force from outside a student (student), related to his own learning activities. In learning activities external motivation from outside the students, both positive and negative, for example; If a student (student) can answer the teacher's questions related to the subject matter with very satisfying answers, then the student can get a positive impetus to work hard to continue to hone his intelligence through learning, so that he

is successful and excels in class and at school. Conversely, if a student is less successful or unable to do the assignments given by the teacher, so that he is reprimanded and given a warning by the teacher, the reprimand and warning is a negative motivation.

Furthermore, Slameto stated the factors that influence learning motivation are as follows:

- a. Internal factors. Internal factors are factors that come from within the individual, which consists of intelligence, talent, attention, motive, maturity, and readiness.
 - Intelligence. Everyone has different intelligence. Students who have high intelligence will be more successful than those who have low intelligence. Students who have a normal level of intelligence can succeed in learning if they study well.
 - Talent. Talent is the ability to learn. This ability will only be realized into real skills after learning or practicing.
 - Caution. To be able to guarantee good learning outcomes, students must pay attention to the subject matter they are studying, if the subject matter does not concern students, then boredom arises, so they no longer like learning. In order for students to study well, try to always attract attention to the subject matter by making sure that the lesson is in accordance with their hobbies or talents.
 - Maturity. Maturity is a level or phase in one's growth. Where the organs of the body are ready to carry out new skills. Learning will be successful if the child is ready (mature).
- b. External factors. External factors are factors that come from outside the child, which includes family factors, school factors, and community factors.
 - Family. The first education a child receives is from the family. Children who learn will receive influence from the family. Including the way parents educate, family member relations, home atmosphere, family economic situation, parents' understanding will be related to children's learning motivation.
 - School factor. School factors influence children's learning motivation, which includes teaching strategies, curriculum, teacher-student relations, student-student relations, school time, building conditions, learning strategies, homework.
 - Community factors. Society also influences student learning, this influence occurs because the presence of children in the community is very close, for example student learning will be influenced by social friends, the mass media, and forms of community life consisting of people who are educated and have good habits and that very influential in increasing student motivation.

Then, according to Priansa, the factors that influence student motivation are personality development.

- a. Student ability. A child's desire needs to be accompanied by the will or skill to achieve it. The desire to read needs to be accompanied by the ability to recognize and pronounce letters. In other words, it can be said that ability will strengthen children's learning motivation.
- b. Student condition. Students' conditions which include physical and spiritual conditions affect learning motivation. Someone who is sick, hungry, or angry will interfere with

learning. On the other hand, students who are healthy and happy are easy to concentrate on.

- c. Student environmental conditions. Student environment can be in the form of natural conditions, living environment, peer association, and social life. As members of society, students can be affected by the environment.
- d. Dynamic elements in learning. Students have feelings, attention, will, memory, and thoughts that experience changes due to life experiences. Experience with friends as an effect on motivation and learning behavior
- e. Efforts of teachers in teaching students. Teachers are developing educators. The teacher's efforts to teach students occur both at school and outside of school.

These learning efforts include:

- a. Understanding of students themselves in the context of compulsory education obligations.
- b. Utilization of reinforcement in the form of gifts, criticism, law quickly.
- c. Educate love of learning.

Kristianto said that the factors that influence Christian education learning motivation in students are:

- a. Physical body. Body organs (such as the brain) that experience limitations or lack of capacity due to the curse (Gen. 3:19) some students have certain deficiencies that affect learning such as visual impairment. Some students experience sleep disturbances, malnutrition or chemical imbalances in their bodies that prevent them from studying.
- b. Psychological pressure
 - Stress. Students experience stress, frustration, or disappointment so that their attention to learning shifts. Traumatized students experience severe stress related to life crises or deviant behavior. Thus, the mental aspect will experience functional abnormalities. They couldn't see ahead because the pain was too severe. However, Christians will overcome the various problems they face. Forgetfulness student memory retention rates vary greatly. Avoid change students persist in the status quo (hardening of categories). They love their daily routine and lifestyle. In learning there is change but there is something that is destructive and often causes pain (Jas. 12).
 - Take the path of low resistance and expect them to learn and grow.
 - Special sin by continuing to self-destruct or through thought patterns (Heb 11:15) some students close themselves to the workings of God's grace that will mature them.
 - Past sin tendencies. If students do not actively declare to serve God, they will easily fall back on past sins (Rom. 6:15-22).
 - Apathy to growth. We cannot assume that all students have the Spirit of God living within them. It is possible that the student never had a personal relationship with Jesus Christ. Without the spirit working within them, they have no interest in spiritual matters (2 Cor. 13:5).

From the opinion above, it can be concluded that the motivation to learn PAK has influencing factors, namely the presence of factors from the students themselves and from outside the students themselves. Factors from the students themselves such as aspirations,

abilities, conditions, and from outside the students such as the environment, elements from the family, and elements from the school such as the teacher's efforts when giving material.

Teachers must try hard to increase student learning motivation. Specifically, teachers need to make certain concrete efforts to increase student learning motivation. A teacher certainly has an effort to foster student learning motivation in order to achieve learning goals. According to Iskandar, the efforts that need to be made by the teacher in motivating students to learn in class are (Purba, 2019):

- a. Explaining learning objectives to students. At the beginning of teaching and learning, a teacher should first explain the Special Instructional Objectives that will be achieved to students.
- b. Prizes/Rewards. Give prizes to outstanding students. This will motivate them to study harder. In addition, students who have not excelled will be motivated to catch up with students who excel.
- c. Competition/competence. The teacher tries to hold competition among students to improve their learning achievement, trying to improve their achievement results.
- d. Compliments. It is appropriate for students who excel to be given awards or praise. Of course, constructive praise.
- e. Punishment. Punishment is given to students who make mistakes during the teaching and learning process. This punishment is given in the hope that the student will change himself and try to spur his learning motivation.
- f. Generating encouragement to students to learn. The strategy is to give maximum attention to students.
- g. Establish good study habits.
- h. Assist students with learning difficulties individually and in groups.
- i. Using a variety of methods, and
- j. Using good media and in accordance with learning objectives.

Furthermore, according to Sardiman, the efforts or methods used to foster student learning motivation are (Abdika et al., 2019):

- a. Provide numbers. Numbers in this case as a symbol of the value of learning activities. Many students' studies, the main thing is to achieve good grades. So that students are usually what is being pursued is test scores or grades on report cards with good numbers. Good numbers for students are a very strong motivation.
- b. Prizes. Rewards can also be said to be motivation, but this is not always the case. Because a prize is for a job, it may not appeal to someone who is displeased and untalented for the job.
- c. Competition/competence. Competition/competence can be used as a motivational tool to encourage student learning. Competition, both individual and group competition can improve student achievement.
- d. Ego-involvement. Raising awareness for students to feel the importance of assignments and accept them as challenges so that they work hard by risking self-esteem, is an important form of motivation.

- e. Giving Deuteronomy. Students will study hard if they know there will be a test. Therefore, giving this test is also a means of motivation. But what the teacher must remember, is not too often (for example every day) because it can be boring and routine.
- f. Know the results. By knowing the results of the work, especially if there is progress, it will encourage students to be more active in learning. The more you know that the graph of learning outcomes increases, the more motivation you have in students to continue learning, with the hope that the results will continue to increase.
- g. Compliments. If there are successful students who successfully complete assignments well, praise should be given. This praise is a form of positive reinforcement as well as good motivation.
- h. Punishment. Punishment as a negative reinforcement but if given properly and wisely can be a motivational tool. Therefore, the teacher must understand the principles of giving punishment.
- i. Passion to learn. The desire to learn means that there is an element of intentionality, there is an intention to learn. The desire to learn means that in students there is motivation to learn, so of course the results will be better.
- j. Interests. Interest and motivation are so closely related. Motivation arises because there is a need, as well as interest so that it is appropriate that interest is the main motivational tool. The learning process will run smoothly if it is accompanied by interest.
- k. Recognized goals. The formulation of goals that are recognized and well received by students, will be a very important motivational tool. Because by understanding the goals that must be achieved, because it is felt to be very useful and profitable, a passion will arise to continue learning.

In line with the opinion above, the priority of ways or efforts that can be made by teachers to motivate students, are as follows:

- a. Provide value. Value is a number obtained from the results of student learning activities that are given according to the results of the tests they have obtained from the results of the teacher's assessment.
- b. Prizes. Prizes are giving something to students who excel in the form of scholarship money, notebooks, or other reading books that are collected in a neatly wrapped box. The goal is to motivate students to maintain learning achievement.
- c. Competence. Competence is competition used as a motivational tool to encourage students to be passionate about learning, both individually and in groups to make the teaching and learning process conducive.
- d. Compliments. Praise that is said at the right time is used as a motivational tool. Praise will raise the soul of students and encourage them to be more passionate about learning.
- e. Punishment. Even though punishment is a negative reinforcement, when done properly and wisely, punishment is a good and effective motivational tool. Punishment educates and aims to improve the attitudes and actions of students who are considered wrong.

From the opinion above, the writer can conclude that there are ways that a teacher can do in arousing student motivation. A teacher can choose the right way to arouse student motivation because each student has different motivations.

5. Principles of student learning motivation

Motivation has an important role in learning activities. No one learns without motivation. No motivation means no learning activities. In order for the role of motivation to be more optimal, it is necessary to pay attention to the principles of motivation in learning. According to Hamalik stated that the principles of learning motivation are as follows

- a. Praise is more effective than punishment. Punishment is stopping an action, while praise is appreciating what has been done. Therefore, praise is more effective in an effort to encourage student learning motivation.
- b. Students have psychological needs (which are basic) that need to be satisfied. These needs manifest in different forms. Students who can meet their needs effectively through learning activities need little help in learning motivation.
- c. Motivation that comes from within the individual is more effective than motivation that comes from outside. Motivation from within gives satisfaction to individuals according to the size that exists within the student himself.

Furthermore, Djamarah explained that there are several principles of motivation in learning, namely:

- a. Motivation as the driving force that encourages learning activities. Someone does learn activities because someone encourages them. Motivation is the basic driving force that encourages someone to learn.
- b. Intrinsic motivation is more important than extrinsic motivation in learning.
- c. Motivation in the form of praise is better than punishment
- d. Motivation is closely related to the need for learning
- e. Motivation can foster optimism in learning
- f. Motivation gives birth to achievement in learning.

Then, Asra said that the principles of learning motivation are as follows:

- a. If the learning material he is studying is meaningful because it is in accordance with his talents, interests, and knowledge, then student learning motivation will increase.
- b. Knowledge, attitudes and skills that have been mastered by students can be used as a basis for mastering knowledge, attitudes and skills.
- c. Student motivation will increase if the teacher is able to become a model for students to watch and imitate.
- d. Learning material or activities presented by the teacher should always be new and different from what has been studied before, thus encouraging students to follow them.
- e. The lessons that students do are appropriate and in accordance with their talents, interests and abilities.
- f. Give sufficient time to students to do the task.
- g. The atmosphere of the learning process is fun and comfortable for students.
- h. The teacher provides a wide opportunity for students to do assignments.
- i. The teacher provides ample opportunities for students to learn according to their learning strategies and techniques.

- j. Can develop students' learning abilities such as logical, systematic, inductive, and deductive thinking.
- k. Students have more control over learning outcomes if there are many senses.
- l. There is friendly and pleasant communication between the teacher and students, so that students are able and dare to express their opinions, according to their level of thinking.

So, the authors conclude that the principle of learning motivation is the basis for moving students to activities in the learning process so that active learning occurs. Intrinsic motivation is better than extrinsic motivation, and praise is better than punishment, and this motivation is basically closely related to needs so that in motivating student learning it is very necessary for the teacher to pay attention to the principles of motivating students.

Conclusion

The Discussion Method is a way of educating that seeks to solve problems which can be in the form of statements or questions, either two or more people each expressing their opinion or making a decision or conclusion on a problem at hand. Motivation is the force that drives individual activities to carry out activities to achieve goals. Motivation can also be said as a plan for success to avoid life's failures. In other words, motivation is a process to achieve a goal. Decreased motivation and boredom in class can lead to disciplinary problems. With the use of the Discussion Method by Christian Religion Teachers and Characteristics, the learning process can be livelier in the classroom atmosphere due to the discussion process between students and with the teacher which makes the learning process more effective, the learning atmosphere is more active, and also the teacher's attention is adjusted to all participants teach in class. With the discussion method by the Christian Religion Teacher and Character, in a person's learning outcomes there is a change in a more positive direction, the level of mental development, which is better when compared to before learning. And get the result in the form of a value made in the form of numbers and symbols.

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